

netWorked Youth Research for Empowerment in the Digital society

Grant Agreement number: 727066

Manifesto Children and Young People

English Version

WP4_D4.1

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H2020-SC6-REV-INEQUAL-2016

Grant Agreement number: 727066

1st November 2016 – 30th September 2019

Requirements document

WP4_D4.1

Deliverable description			
Filename	WYRED_WP4_D4.1_Manifesto Children and Young People_version.1		
Type	R		
Dissemination level	PU		
Due Date (in months)	2		
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.376849		
Deliverable contributors			
Version No.	Name, Institution	Role	Last update
1	WYRED Consortium	Author	12 /03 / 2017

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1 Introductory note

A central aim of the WYRED project (García-Peñalvo, 2016; García-Peñalvo & Kearney, 2016) is to give children and young people a voice, particularly in relation to research into issues that concern them, and how its results are discussed and presented.

A manifesto written by the consortium exists to declare our intentions. We hope that the children and young people participating in WYRED will contribute to their own manifesto.

With the help of a group of young people in Belgium, we have created a “seed” manifesto, with some bullet points to start, but we cannot do more, since this manifesto should represent the voices of children and young people.

This will be placed on a wiki page on the WYRED platform (García-Peñalvo & Durán-Escudero, 2017). All the children and young people participating can add ideas or comment.

2 Seed manifesto

- We, young people, have always been perceived as “the future”. We are seen as “agents of change”, “shapers of our societies” or “drivers of new behaviours and understandings”.
- Unfortunately, we are not often listened to, and we are not free to shape our world. We are seen to as “users”, the objects of others decisions.
- We are seen as a homogenous group: “the young”. But we are we are diverse. We feel our immense diversity should be respected. Each of us has their own complex identity, background and attitudes that create our own sense of self, which cannot be reduced to a single element or aspect.
- We feel our freedoms are not respected. We need to be able to exercise our freedoms without fear of being judged for who we are, but also to stay safe. We feel this world is not well adapted to our needs.
- We did not live in the pre-digital era. We have not had to “adapt to technology”. Our world has always had a digital dimension that is an indivisible part of it. But our world was and is being shaped by others, without us having a say.

- We want to have our say, we want to be able to define our rules, rights, expectations, responsibilities and obligations. We do not want to be passive “users”.
- The digital world we inhabit is blurred. Reality and virtuality overlap, as do distinctions between human, machines and nature. We have our own understandings of this changing space and the potential it has, and our potential within it, and we want to explore these issues.
- We believe our perceptions can shape society, and the way our role in it is understood. We welcome the chance to voice our concerns and explore them to find potential solutions and insights to share with society.
- We also welcome the safe space WYRED provides, where we can embrace our diversity in a spirit of equality, where all our individual natures can engage and contribute and where we can explore actively and creatively.

3 References

- García-Peñalvo, F. J. (2016). The WYRED Project: A Technological Platform for a Generative Research and Dialogue about Youth Perspectives and Interests in Digital Society. *Journal of Information Technology Research*, 9(4), vi-x.
- García-Peñalvo, F. J., & Durán-Escudero, J. (2017). *Interaction design principles in WYRED platform*. Paper presented at the HCI INTERNATIONAL 2017, Vancouver, Canada.
- García-Peñalvo, F. J., & Kearney, N. A. (2016). Networked youth research for empowerment in digital society. The WYRED project. In F. J. García-Peñalvo (Ed.), *Proceedings of the Fourth International Conference on Technological Ecosystems for Enhancing Multiculturality (TEEM'16) (Salamanca, Spain, November 2-4, 2016)* (pp. 3-9). New York, NY, USA: ACM.